

THE RESULT OF THE CURRENT AND STEP-BY-STEP PEDAGOGICAL CONTROL METHODOLOGY IN THE COURSE OF PEDAGOGICAL RESEARCH

Shavkatova Mohinabonu Oybek qizi

student of the Uzbekistan state world language university

Zulxumor Xatamovna Bannopova

Scientific adviser: senior teacher of State world language university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17303409>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st October 2025

Accepted: 04th October 2025

Online: 09th October 2025

KEYWORDS

step-by-step assessment, students' knowledge level during the lesson and can adjust teaching methods, methodological system determines the relevance of the research

ABSTRACT

One of the important tasks in the educational process is to identify and develop student's knowledge, skills, and competencies. Pedagogical assessment is an integral part of this process, as it ensures the quality and effectiveness of education. In particular, the scientific application of various assessment methods in modern education plays a significant role in increasing students' activity and intellectual potential.

Introduction.

In pedagogical research, two types of assessment methods are widely used: current (continuous) assessment and step-by-step assessment. Current assessment focuses on regularly monitoring students' knowledge during the lesson, while step-by-step assessment aims to determine the overall level of students' development at the end of specific stages of education.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the results of these two assessment methods in pedagogical research, to reveal their impact on the activities of both students and teachers, and to draw scientifically based conclusions. Thus, the article highlights the theoretical and practical aspects of assessment and includes the views of both foreign and local scholars. If we determine students' daily progress, continuous pedagogical assessment becomes one of the most important parts of the learning process. This is because it allows for the regular monitoring of students' knowledge, the identification of their level of preparation for lessons, and the early detection of difficulties in learning. The outcome of such assessment is that students develop the habit of consistently reinforcing their knowledge, studying regularly, and maintaining discipline. At the same time, the teacher gains a clear understanding of students' knowledge level during the lesson and can adjust teaching methods or provide additional explanations where necessary. As a result, the educational process becomes more effective, and active communication between the student and teacher is established.

The methods and means of confirming the integration of general and specialized subjects in the of tailoring of the educational process based on the methodology of integratise subjects. the essence. theory and practice of interdisciplinary integration, the main didactic functions, the factors affecting the basis of the integration of subjects arc discussed in this article.

Key sturdy: tailoring, integration educational process, educational mtg.-Tatum scientific research. effectiveness of educational rftVeVi. enterprise practice.

In today's rapidly changing world, the integration of students practical skills with the process of enterprise practice by engineer-mlagogues in higher educational institutions in the technical field is an important factor in the training of mature specialists. Pedagogical experts around the world are conducting scientific research on the development and introduction of scientifically based advanced educational technologies and information technologies into the educational process. improving regulatory documents, and improving the quality of education. Enhancing the quality of education, training competitive personnel, effective organization of scientific and innovative activities. development of international eixiperation. innovative activities in education, research attention is being paid to scientific research related to the wide introduction of results into practice. the commercialization of scientific developments. and the attraction of talented young people to scientific and research work. The demand of creating environment fin. the training of specialists with professional skills and high qualifications. to organic the educational process based on the methodology of integration of disciplines, and to scientifically substantiate the fonnalion and development in accordance with socio-economic conditions, as well as the need to develop a methodological system determines the relevance of the research. According to the analysis of the research works a foreign and our scientists, the indhodical training system of highly qualified specialists, the essence, theory and practice of interdisciplinary integration. the main didactic functions and principles are explained by rise study of integrative disciplines in technical higher education institutions. The importance of interdisciplinary integration in the educational process is not only the versatility of this connection, but also its manifestation and rnethids of its use Particularly, the mobile•didactic support of the specialty subject "Technology of sew ing, knitting and goldsanithing", which gives students the opportunity to learn general and specialized subjects. has been improved on the basis of scientific and methodological approaches. On the basis of "Mobile-learning". BOYD (Bring your own device - use of a mobile device in education) technologies and the principles of digitization of education, cintent.iniproml mobile applications were created, which included informational and didactic matenals consisting of short video clips used for lectures and practical training.

"Similarly, a study conducted in the Division of Lipa City investigated the pedagogical adjustments of Mathematics teachers who were required to teach outside their specialization. The findings revealed that It has been observed that there are Mathematics teachers in some schools who are assigned to teach subjects other than their field of specialization. Being assigned to teach other disciplines requires a sense of efficacy, subject matter knowledge and pedagogical knowledge for these teachers. Hence, this study determined the pedagogical adjustments of Mathematics teachers handling other disciplines in selected national high schools at the Division of Lipa City. Specifically, it dealt with the respondents' assessment on their pedagogical adjustments in teaching other discipline and the suggested activities that may help the respondents adjust their pedagogical practices to the demands of the subjects they are teaching. Results revealed that the respondents are adjusted pedagogically by summarizing important points and considering the students' existing knowledge and experiences when discussing the lesson. They also give challenging but doable tasks to their students and help

students to learn effectively through varied activities. The above-mentioned findings recommend that Mathematics education supervisors may initiate the conduct of seminars in utilizing the appropriate strategies for in-service Mathematics teachers who are teaching other disciplines. It is also recommended that future researches be done contemplating on the effectiveness of the activities suggested for the benefit of the students.

PEDAGOGICAL PREPARATION OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF PRACTICAL TEACHING

C. Serafin Faculty of Education, Palacky University in Olomouc (CZECH REPUBLIC)

Abstract The article focuses on changes in the specialized higher education of teacher training in the bachelor study programme Teacher Training in Practical Teaching and Vocational Training. This study is focused on preparing teachers of practical teaching for teaching at secondary vocational schools in the Czech Republic, in accordance with the Act on Pedagogical Staff, which codifies the basic conditions for graduate destinations in the Czech Republic. Relatively substantial changes in higher education are currently taking place in the Czech Republic due to the amendment to the Higher Education Act and there is a change in the process of accreditation of all higher education programmes, including the so-called institutional accreditations. These changes can also be taken as a stimulus for new perspectives on the training of higher education graduates in their professional experience. The article presents the basic attributes of these changes, which fundamentally modernize their preparation for destinations in the fields of education providing secondary education with the vocational certificate and the secondary school-leaving exam (the 'maturita' exam). In brief, the graduate will have the necessary knowledge and skills to work as a teacher of practical teaching and vocational subjects focused on either trade and services or engineering (mechanics I engineering, electrical engineering, technology) at the professional and didactic level. The emphasis should be placed on didactics and thorough pedagogical-psychological preparation. The problems related to the specializations should be addressed in the didactics of vocational subjects. The knowledge, skills and attitudes gained during the study form the basis of the competences for practicing the teaching of practical teaching and vocational training. However, these competences also give full qualification for working in institutions involved in the relevant field of education (training courses, retraining, professional qualification, further education, etc.), also as a teacher of vocational and leisure time education in various educational institutions and in corporate education, etc.

Advanced democratic societies with a developed economy, science, technology, and culture make rising demands of people, their level of education, or general growth. Logically, this is accompanied by increasing requirements of general education, vocational training, and naturally also language skills. Our society gives younger generations access to all levels of education, depending on their individual interests and skills; it seeks to form citizens with a universal education, both knowledge-, and practice-wise. This emphasis of education and guidance is closely related to the requirements made of scientific disciplines which systematically pursue such activities. Guidance, or rather education itself comes with numerous issues, studied and comprehensively addressed by pedagogy whose important scientific goal is to define guidance and education. Pedagogy develops goals, character and volition, mental and physical skills, and the content of education. It sets the tasks for guidance and education, and explores the most effective tools for meeting set goals, i.e. methods and forms of work. In

pedagogy, theory of education and teaching is addressed by didactics. Didactics deals with the issues of educational goals, tasks, content, and methods of education. It relies mostly on pedagogical findings, but also addresses the rules of communicating knowledge, in close relation to other disciplines, such as psychology, philosophy, gnoseology, logics.

References:

- [1]. Siddikova Sadoqat Ghaforovna rector of Bukhara Engineering - Technological Institute and, Doctor of Philosophy in pedagogical science Sadoqats@mail.ru
- [2]. Nora V. Marasigan Associate professor, college of teacher education Batangas state University JPLPC - Malvar, Batangas, Philippines corresponding author E-mail: yayi_manasigan@yahoo.cov
- [3]. C. Serafin Faculty of education, Palacky university in Olomous (CZECH Republic)
- [4]. Zahid Ali, Dr Maggie Busch, Dr Muhammad Nasim Qaisrani, Dr Hidayat Ur Rehman.
- [5]. Methodology of pedagogy ppt.pptx

